

ADOPTING A LINGUOCULTURAL METHOD FOR EDUCATING PROSPECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE EXPERTS

^aOKSANA SNIGOVSKA, ^bOLHA REMBACH, ^cMARIANA BRODA, ^dLARYSA MOSHIEVYCH, ^eOLHA SHUM

^a*Odesa I. I. Mechnikov National University, Odesa, Ukraine.*

^b*Leonid Uzkov Khmelnytskyi University of Management and Law, Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine.*

^c*Drohobych Ivan Franko State Pedagogical University, Drohobych, Ukraine.*

^d*Zaporizhzhia National University, Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine.*

^e*Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine.*
email:

^a*snigovska@ukr.net*, ^b*olga.ukr@ukr.net*, ^c*mariana.broda@dspu.edu.ua*, ^d*larisamosiyevich1977@gmail.com*, ^e*oshym@ukr.net*

Abstract: The article is dedicated to exploring the prospects and features of implementing a linguocultural approach in teaching English as a foreign language within the framework of cognitive-linguocultural methodology for developing students' foreign language competence in higher education institutions. The research is based on the comprehensive application of the methods of analysis and synthesis, forecasting and data analysis, pedagogical observation, surveying, and generalisation. The article provides a critical review of scientific works dedicated to the linguocultural approach, describes the interrelationship between the English language and culture, formulates methodological recommendations for integrating the linguocultural approach into the educational process, and outlines an experiment conducted on the application of the linguocultural approach in the process of learning English at a higher educational institution in Ukraine. It has been established that the linguocultural approach to studying English fosters the development of the following competencies: cultural studies, general cultural, linguistic and cultural studies, linguocultural, sociocultural, and communicative. Forming foreign language communication includes mastering the ethical norms of communication and reflecting on the mental characteristics of a particular linguistic and cultural community. To effectively implement the linguocultural approach, it is essential to apply this principle comprehensively and consistently in all aspects of language learning: speaking, listening, writing, and reading. It has been proven that the role of the teacher in the educational process increases with the implementation of the linguocultural approach. However, the teacher must have an appropriate cultural background, deepen their knowledge of other people's cultural heritage and mental characteristics, and constantly improve their linguocultural level not only from theoretical sources but also from personal observations of native speakers, which requires significant time and financial investment.

Keywords: Linguocultural approach, Foreign language learning, English language, Culture, National concept sphere, Cognitive linguistics, Language competence, Speech competence, Linguocultural Competence, Secondary linguistic personality

1 Introduction

Nowadays, no one who teaches or learns a foreign language doubts the necessity of developing foreign language, linguistic, and speech competencies through the unity of language and culture. The cultural platform serves as a unique foundation of every society, as does its national heritage, and language acts to transmit and interpret this heritage.

In modern linguodidactics, the concept of "foreign language" has been expanded to the level of "foreign language education". Thus, the object of study becomes the language and the linguoculture. This can be seen as a radical shift in the target orientations in foreign language learning, as the expected program outcomes of higher education include training specialists who are not only proficient in a foreign language at the level of functional literacy and professional communication but also ready to establish professional intercultural and international contacts. For this reason, most foreign language curricula include the formation of intercultural communicative competence among the core competencies of future specialists.

Learning a foreign language involves mastering effective tactics and strategies for oral and written, consecutive or simultaneous translation. It also aims to shape the student's personality and develop competencies that will enable them to make effective decisions in a globalised world. Therefore, professional foreign language competence must consider the peculiarities of intercultural communication, which entails forming and maintaining one's cultural identity and accepting and understanding the values of representatives of other cultures. In this context, modern linguistic science defines the linguocultural

approach to foreign language teaching as one that promotes the formation of intercultural professional communicative competence in learners. This approach is based on the understanding that alongside learning foreign languages, it is necessary to study the culture, worldview, and mentality of the people who speak that language. Given this, foreign language teachers need to realise that it is also crucial to determine cultural knowledge that will allow for professional foreign language communication along with linguistic knowledge and the formation of communicative skills.

This article aims to explore the prospects and features of implementing a linguocultural approach in foreign language teaching within the framework of cognitive-linguocultural methodology for developing foreign language competence. The research is based on English language materials.

The main research objectives set by the authors of the article are to conduct a critical review of scientific works dedicated to the linguocultural approach, describe the interrelation between the English language and culture, formulate methodological recommendations for integrating the linguocultural approach into the educational process, and outline an experiment conducted on the application of the linguocultural approach in the process of learning English at a higher educational institution in Ukraine.

2 Literature Review

An analytical and critical review of scientific works (Balgopal et al., 2017; Bautista-Puig et al., 2021; Hossain, 2024; Vishal et al., 2024) allows us to assert that the problem of the interrelation between language and culture, the study of language, and the parallel understanding of culture are essential focuses of modern linguistics and linguodidactics. The first scientist to describe the relationship between language and culture was Humboldt (1876), whose scientific concept is that both material and spiritual culture are embodied in language. Hadjieva and Djumambetova Dilfuza (2023) proposed their methodological system for studying English stylistics based on the linguocultural approach. Carr and Kitinger (2021) consider the role of linguistic stereotypes in learning foreign languages. Researcher Chen (2008) selects song material as one of the ways to implement the approach we are studying. Scholar Hossain (2024) aptly notes that the teacher should recognise the relevance of integrating language and culture and implement this integration daily in the classroom. Researchers Shytyk and Akimova (2020), Akimova et al. (2023) examine linguoculture in the context of psycholinguistics. Kitao (2000) formulated methodological recommendations for English teachers in the USA regarding the peculiarities of studying culture in foreign language learning. Dr. Mohammed AbdAlla AbdAlgane Mohammed (2020a, 2020b) focused his scientific attention on studying English-speaking culture and learning English in the Arab cultural environment, while scholar Saloomeh Jahanforouz (2018) sees the study of national literature as one of the main ways to implement the linguocultural approach.

Ukrainian researcher Haiduchenko (2010) studied the problem of forming linguocultural competence among university students based on paremiological texts and aphorisms. The scientist defines linguocultural competence as "a system of knowledge about culture and a set of skills to operate this knowledge in specific linguistic situations". Scholar Kolisnychenko considers linguocultural competence an integral characteristic of the learner's personality, and in her opinion, the approach we are studying "harmonises the process of cultural dialogue". Kolesnyk (2014) explored the theoretical foundations and didactic prerequisites for implementing the linguocultural approach in foreign language learning.

Researchers Ostapenko and Udovichenko (2019) view cognitive linguistics and the linguocultural approach to language study as leading paradigms of modern linguistics. The researchers claim that modern linguistics is dominated by three scientific paradigms of language study – anthropocentric, comparative-historical, and system-structural. Within each of these paradigms, the linguocultural approach can be implemented (Kramsch et al., 1996; Kramsch, 2001). Researcher Pevna (2013) considers the linguocultural approach to teaching English as a tool for forming the student's subjective position. According to the scholar, “language is not only a part of culture but also largely a culture-forming part”, as language changes often occur under the influence of culture and vice versa, cultural changes immediately determine linguistic changes (new words appear, existing words become archaic, linguistic intonation and tone change). Researcher Vdovina (2003) examines the linguocultural approach to language teaching in terms of developing a methodology for teaching future foreign language teachers to read English literary texts. Halenko (2012) defines cultural competence as one of the main components in the structure of professional competencies for students of philological specialities. Cultural competence is necessary to adequately understand modern Internet discourse texts (Akimova et al., 2022). Suweni et al. (2022) determine the very process of learning a foreign language by the cultural characteristics of students.

3 Research methods

The aim and research objectives outlined in the article necessitated the comprehensive combination of the following scientific methods:

The analysis and synthesis method was used to critically review scientific literature and elucidate the essence of the linguocultural approach to teaching English as a foreign language:

- The method of pedagogical observation allowed for the analysis of the latest trends in foreign language teaching and the subsequent adjustment of the results of implementing the linguocultural approach.
- The survey method was employed to study the pedagogical experience of higher education scientific and pedagogical staff regarding the peculiarities of implementing the studied approach to language teaching.
- The forecasting and data analysis method was used to analyse survey data from teachers and form the expected program outcomes of teaching English as a foreign language after applying the linguocultural approach.
- The generalisation method was utilised to formulate the research's scientific and theoretical conclusions and summarise the pedagogical experiment's results.

4 Results

The linguocultural approach considers the mutual influences of language and culture, which is especially important in globalisation. When learning a foreign language, one must consider the behavioural reactions inherent to a particular nation and understand the language as a means of interpreting collective experiences encoded in it. Linguocultural studies define a concept as a cultural unit endowed with figurative, semantic, and value components (Savchak, 2016).

In our opinion, the linguocultural approach to learning foreign languages should be based on the following methodologies and theories:

1. Theory of intercultural communication.
2. Cognitive-linguocultural methodology.
3. Theory of modelling foreign language education.

Studying the system of linguocultural units is worth applying the method of linguocultural fields, which is methodologically realised through studying overarching cultural themes. Implementing the linguocultural approach to foreign language learning should be carried out through the content of the discipline “Foreign Language”, represented at each level through cognitive-linguocultural complexes. For example, at the B1-B2 level, the following cognitive-linguocultural problem complexes can be offered to learners:

1. Environmental issues in the countries whose language is being studied.
2. Cultural and historical heritage.
3. State system and legal institutions.
4. Religious and national holidays.
5. Art, music, and literature of the countries whose language is being studied.
6. Prominent figures.
7. History of nation-building.
8. History of state formation.
9. Commemorative days and their historical significance.

The selection of linguocultural material for educational purposes should consider the following recommendations:

1. Linguocultural material used in the educational process should form an accurate, not distorted, understanding of another culture and reality, meaning the selected material should be endowed with meaningful values.
2. Determine how well the selected material forms an understanding of critical concepts of linguocultural studies, such as “cultural dialogue”, “cultural heritage”, “cultural diversity”, and “multicultural personality”.
3. The material selection should consider the learners' intellectual and age levels.

The next urgent issue that needs to be addressed is the development of specific methods, techniques, and forms for implementing the linguocultural approach in the educational process. To form this complex of methods, techniques, and forms, we propose the following tactics:

- Familiarising learners with folklore and literary heritage of national literatures.
- Contextual learning.
- Transforming into the role of a native speaker through situational learning technology (case study) by solving sociocultural and linguocultural tasks.
- Highlight so-called “linguocultures” in texts prepared for classroom or home reading and define the content of these linguocultures.
- Using authentic materials (vlogs, microblogs, news releases, reports, films, cartoons, comics).
- Using modern information technologies in learning, including mobile learning, participating in video conferences and virtual tours of significant cities and museums of the countries whose language is being studied.

The implementation of the linguocultural approach is closely related to the communicative-cognitive approach to studying English as a foreign language, mainly:

1. Focusing teachers' attention on teaching typical models of speech behaviour.
2. The sociocultural context of professional language learning.
3. Selecting such lexical material, reading, and listening materials that promote a better understanding of the cultural characteristics of the English-speaking society.
4. Gradually forming an English-speaking worldview.

Implementing the linguocultural approach to learning a foreign language requires gradualness, systematicity, and consistency in all speech activities: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Table 1 presents the expected program outcomes of learning.

Table 1. Projected programme outcomes of English language teaching using the linguistic and cultural approach

Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing
Students understand cultural information by ear and can feel the peculiarities of national (English-speaking) intonation.	Students build monologues and dialogues using vocabulary to describe cultural realities, customs and traditions, national holidays, and national food and drinks. They correctly pronounce geographical and topographical names and demonstrate knowledge of national heroes. Students know the rules of etiquette in English and have strategies for communicating with native English speakers.	Students read and fully understand texts on sociocultural topics, demonstrate an understanding of the essential cultural background, discuss issues raised in the text, answer questions, and recognise emotionally charged vocabulary.	Students can create formal and informal texts using nationally marked vocabulary, English phraseology, proverbs, and sayings created by the English-speaking culture. They can adhere to the appropriate tone of written communication and use stable expressions of the English language.

Source: author's conception

The linguocultural approach considers the mutual influences of language and culture, which is particularly important in globalisation. When studying a foreign language, it is essential to consider the behavioural reactions inherent to a particular nation and understand language as a means of interpreting collective experiences encoded in it. The linguocultural approach defines a concept as a cultural unit endowed with figurative, semantic, and value components (Hyde, 2008).

The lexical composition of the English language, which contains cultural concepts, can be classified into three groups:

1. Non-equivalent vocabulary has no single-word translation in other languages as it names specific cultural phenomena. This vocabulary is called exoticisms and ethnographisms, symbolising rather than revealing another culture. For example, words like a speaker, shilling, and cricket are always associated with England.
2. Lacunae – the absence of words for meanings expressed in other languages. Lacunae can be noticed only by comparing languages. The reasons for their emergence are due to differences in cultural functioning. For example, the English word lawyer means a legal professional, but the English culture has various types of lawyers with specific words: advocate – a senior lawyer; counsellor – a court advisor; counsel – a legal advisor; solicitor – a consultant for clients and firms, with the right to appear in lower courts; barrister – a lawyer with the right to appear in higher courts; attorney – a legal representative. Most languages do not have such a gradation of the legal profession, so the word lawyer is often

used, while the other terms essentially become lacunae when translated into other languages.

3. Background vocabulary consists of words or phrases with additional meaning due to semantic or stylistic nuances. Background vocabulary reflects knowledge about social reality.

As we can see, the linguocultural approach is related to understanding and reproducing the linguistic picture of the world. Each language “paints” its linguistic picture, and reconstructing this picture becomes the main task of modern linguistic semantics.

Learning speech units in connection with specific speech situations is crucial to successfully implementing the linguocultural approach in foreign language teaching, especially English. To create these situations, authentic teaching materials that allow immersion in the intercultural environment and multimedia technologies in the educational process are appropriate. These technologies significantly expand the possibilities of modelling speech situations and help organise real-time communication with native speakers. Integrating cultural studies knowledge into language learning by visualising national characteristics is also beneficial.

In a competency-based approach to teaching English, we must emphasise that the linguocultural approach to learning English will contribute to forming the following competencies: cultural, general cultural, linguistic and cultural, linguocultural, sociocultural, and communicative (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Competencies developed by applying the linguistic and cultural approach

Source: author's conception

General cultural competence is the ability to explore and evaluate the main cultural achievements of the native language speakers. Cultural competence involves understanding the traditions, customs, and religious rituals of the people whose language the learner is studying and being able to analyse the

commonalities and differences in these traditions compared to their native culture. Linguistic and cultural competence involves mastering the features of English language speakers' verbal and non-verbal (paralinguistic) behaviour. Communicative competence, as one of the dominant areas in training foreign

language specialists, involves the ability to use English in all spheres, genres, and personal and public speech styles. Sociocultural competence will allow future specialists to interpret cultural differences, communicate effectively in a multicultural environment with various social groups, and master the rules of speech etiquette, applying them in communication practice. Linguocultural competence aims to create and adjust a foreign language worldview, forming the learner's secondary linguistic personality. This competence includes knowledge of the rules for greetings and farewells in the English-speaking world, rules for conducting discussions, and the basic principles of intercultural communication.

During the 2023–2024 academic year, the authors surveyed 38 English language teachers regarding the effectiveness of using the linguocultural approach to developing English language competence. The survey was conducted at Odesa I. I. Mechnikov National University and Leonid Uzkov Khmelnytskyi University of Management and Law. According to the survey results, 87% of the surveyed teachers consider the linguocultural approach effective for developing English language competence. 74% of teachers regularly use texts on sociocultural topics, collections of aphorisms, phraseological dictionaries, and works of British and American literature as teaching materials. 88% of respondents use authentic sources for listening exercises. 62% of teachers need more methodological developments, textbooks, and manuals with a linguocultural thematic focus. Most respondents (67%) consider integrating linguocultural material into each practical lesson appropriate, while 33% believe using this type of teaching material several times a semester is sufficient.

During the survey, English language teachers' proposals for more effectively implementing the linguocultural approach to teaching were processed and analysed. These proposals can be summarised into the following educational recommendations: involving native speakers, such as diaspora representatives, in the educational process, conducting seminars and master classes, integrated cultural courses for teachers, or specialised courses for students.

5 Discussion

We fully agree with the position of the scholar Pevna (2013) that for the effective implementation of the linguocultural approach, it is vital to apply it consistently in combination with other approaches, implementing it in all aspects of language learning, that is, the four main types of speech activities (speaking, listening, writing, and reading), as well as organising learning based on the principles of novelty and authenticity of materials. However, implementing the linguocultural approach increases the role of the teacher in the educational process. Therefore, the teacher must have an appropriate cultural background and visit English-speaking countries to share cultural experiences not only from theoretical sources but also from personal observations, which is especially valuable for students. However, such linguocultural training for teachers requires significant time and financial investment.

The teacher may encounter specific difficulties in implementing the linguocultural approach. Students, when learning a foreign language, have to form a secondary linguistic personality by restructuring their thinking, which is inseparable from speech, and forming cultural elements from another linguoculture in their consciousness. This often occurs through comparing their language and culture with the foreign one.

We believe that the implementation of the linguocultural approach is closely related to the communicative-cognitive approach to studying English as a foreign language, particularly:

1. Focusing teachers' attention on teaching typical models of speech behaviour.
2. The sociocultural context of professional language learning.
3. Selecting lexical material, reading, and listening materials that promote a better understanding of the cultural characteristics of the English-speaking society.
4. Gradually forming an English-speaking worldview.

6 Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded that the linguocultural approach to teaching foreign languages involves identifying speech units with specific features of verbal expression in the native language and the language being studied. Forming foreign language communication includes mastering the ethical norms of communication and reflecting on the mental characteristics of a particular linguistic and cultural community. This will allow learners to adequately formulate their thoughts in a foreign language in specific situations. Equally important is mastering conversational clichés and fixed expressions relevant to communication topics. In this case, information sources can be monolingual dictionaries, authentic materials, works of fiction or journalism, and the opportunities provided by modern computer technologies. Success in mastering a foreign language is determined by acquiring the language structure through an inseparable connection with speech situations.

The method of pedagogical observation showed that the linguocultural approach to teaching English as a foreign language contributed to increasing students' motivation levels due to their interest in the cultural characteristics of native speakers, expanding their vocabulary by mastering proverbs and the phraseological level of the language, and improving the cultural level of the student as a whole. The conducted research does not claim to be definitive and exhaustive in its results. However, it fully reflects the main trends of modern education, particularly learning foreign languages.

The prospects for further research are multidisciplinary studies at the intersection of linguodidactics, cultural studies, psycholinguistics, and country studies. It will provide a detailed description of the algorithms for implementing the linguocultural approach to learning foreign languages.

Literature:

1. Akimova, N., Akimova, A., & Akimova, A.: Specificity of internet texts understanding in youth age. *Psycholinguistics*, 2022, 32(1), 6–28. <http://doi.org/10.31470/2309-1797-2022-32-1-6-28>
2. Akimova, N., Chornous, O., Akimova, A., & Akimova, A.: Psychological peculiarities of understanding brand name in form of personal name. *Psycholinguistics*, 2023, 33(1), 6–25. <http://doi.org/10.31470/2309-1797-2023-33-1-6-25>
3. Balgopal, M. M., Wallace, A. M., & Dahlberg, S.: Writing from different cultural contexts: How college students frame an environmental SSI through written arguments. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 2017, 54, 195–218. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/am-pdf/10.1002/tea.21342>
4. Bautista-Puig, N., Aleixo, A. M., Leal, S., Azeiteiro, U., & Costas, R.: Unveiling the research landscape of sustainable development goals and their inclusion in higher education institutions and research centers: Major trends in 2000–2017. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 2021, 2, art. no. 620743. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2021.620743>
5. Carr, S. C., & Kitzinger, C.: Media representations of accents and their influence on linguistic stereotypes. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 2021, 40 (5), 589–610.
6. Chen, W.: The use of songs in teaching foreign languages. *Foreign Language Annals*, 2008, 41(2), 235–252. <https://doi.org/10.2137/145960611797471552>
7. Hadjieva, D. T., & Djumambetova, D. K.: Teaching English stylistics through linguacultural approach to EFL student. *International Journal of Education Humanities and Social Science*, 2023, 11(9), 505–512. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371644>
8. Haiduchenko, L.: Formuvannia linhvokulturnoi kompetentsii studentiv v protsesi vyvchennia inozemnykh mov na materialii aforystychnykh ta paremiolohichnykh tekstiv. *Problemy semantyky, prahmatyky ta kohnityvnoi linhvistyky*, 2010, 17, 90–97. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/psptk1_2010_17_13
9. Halenko, A.: Cultural competence in the structure of professional competences of students of philological specialties.

Scientific Bulletin of Donbass, 2012, 4. <http://nvd.luguniv.edu.ua/archiv/NN20/12gamsfs.pdf>

10. Hossain, K.: Reviewing the role of culture in English language learning: Challenges and opportunities for educators. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2024, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100781>

11. Humboldt, K. W. (1876): The heterogeneity of language and its influence on the intellectual development of mankind. *Phainomena*, 2006, 55, 45–50. <https://philpapers.org/rec/VONTHO-2>

12. Hyde, M.: Intercultural Competence in English language education. *Modern English Teacher*, 2008, 7(2), 7–11. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285818498_Intercultural_competence_in_English_language_education

13. Jahanforouz, S.: The Role of Literature and Culture in English Language Teaching. (2018). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325258386_The_Role_of_Literature_and_Culture_in_English_Language_Teaching

14. Kitao, K.: Teaching Culture in Foreign Language Instruction in the Unites States. (2000). <http://ilc2.doshisha.ac.jp/users/kkitao/library/article/culture.htm>

15. Kolesnyk, K.: Application of the linguistic and cultural approach in teaching the New Greek language in general educational institutions of Ukraine. *Scientific Notes of the Ternopil Volodymyr Hnatiuk National Pedagogical University. Series: Pedagogy*, 2014, 1, 93–99. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/NZTNPU_ped_2014_1_18

16. Kramsch, C.: *Language and Culture*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001.

17. Kramsch, C., Cain, A., & Murphy-Lejeune, E.: Why should language teachers teach culture? *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 1996, 9(1), 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908319609525221>

18. Mohammed, M. AA. AA.: The Impact of Culture on English Language Learning. *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature (IJSELL)*, 2020a, 8(1), 21–27. <http://doi.org/10.20431/2347-3134.0801003>

19. Mohammed, M. AA. AA.: Utilizing Technology in ELT Classrooms. *Open Access Library Journal*, 2020b, 7, e6016. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1106016>

20. Ostapenko, S., & Udovichenko, H.: Linguocultural approach to language learning and cognitive linguistics as basic notions of modern language studies. *Southern Archive (Philological Sciences)*, 2019, 77, 60–65. <https://doi.org/10.32999/ksu2663-2691/2019-77-11>

21. Pevna, S. Ye.: Basic approaches to English language teaching in the context of students' subject position formation. *Education and Pedagogical Sciences*, 2013, 2, 37–42. https://pedagogicaljournal.luguniv.edu.ua/archive/2013/N2/articles/6/Pevna_ua.pdf

22. Savchak, I.: Linguo-cultural approach to foreign language teaching of international relations specialists. *The Scientific Issues of Ternopil Volodymyr Hnatiuk National Pedagogical University. Series: Pedagogy*, 2016, (4), 108–115. <http://nzp.tnpu.edu.ua/article/view/93923>

23. Shytyk, L., & Akimova, A.: Ways of transferring the internal speech of characters: Psycholinguistic projection. *Psycholinguistics*, 2020, 27(2), 361–384. <https://doi.org/10.31470/2309-1797-2020-27-2-361-384>

24. Suweni, D., Ruswanto, R., & Prasmoro, B.: The Importance of Culture Recognition in Teaching English. *Journal of Applied Linguistics Indonesia (Aplinesia)*, 2022, 06(1), 8–17.

25. Vdovina, T. O.: Methods of teaching future foreign language teachers to read English literary texts. PhD thesis. Kyiv, 2003. <http://www.disslib.org/metodyka-navchannja-majbutnikh-uchyteliv-inozemnoyi-movy-chytannja-anhliyskykh-khudozhnikh.html>

26. Vishal, K., Sanjiv, K., & Rajni, S.: Environmental socio-scientific issues as contexts in developing scientific literacy in science education: A systematic literature review. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2024, 9, art. no. 100765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100765>

Primary Paper Section: A

Secondary Paper Section: AI, AM